

07 MARCH 2025

**WOLFSON RESEARCH EXCHANGE
UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK**

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

IRRESISTIBLE

DECAY

**DISCOURSES OF DEATH
IN LIFE FROM THE 18TH
CENTURY TO TODAY**

09:00-09:30	Registration and Arrival
09:30-09:45	Welcome and Introductory remarks
09:45-11:15	Session 1 - REX1&2: Decaying policies and discourses Session 2 - REX 3: Material decomposition
11:15-11:30	Break
11:30-12:30	Keynote 1 - REX 1&2: Sarah Lamble “A queer society is a ruined society”. The irresistible decay of the contemporary anti-gender culture wars
12:30-13:30	Lunch
13:30-15:00	Session 3 - REX1&2: Urban decay and resistance Session 4 - REX 3: Narrating the abject
15:00-15:15	Coffee break
15:15-16:15	Keynote 2 - REX 1&2: Corinna Wagner Photographing Things in Ruins
16:15-16:30	Coffee break
16:30-18:00	Session 5 - REX 1&2: New and old technologies Session 6 - REX 3: Documenting death
18:00-18:30	Closing remarks

Session 1 : Decaying policies and discourses

Chair: TBC

- Arnaud Miranda (Political theory, Sciences Po), 'Politics of Decay: A Metaphorology of Decadence' – Online
 - Ash Stokoe (Political Science and International Studies, University of Birmingham), 'The death of liberal inclusion: trans rights in Tory Britain (2018- 2024)'
 - Romain Chenet (Global Sustainable Development, University of Warwick), 'The decayed discourse of global development: a premature or overdue post-mortem?' – Online
 - Seth Compaoré (French, Austin College), 'Zombies and/or possessed bodies as form of Resistance in Atlantics- a transatlantic legacy' – Online
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Session 2: Material decomposition

Chair: TBC

- Emma Dove (English, University of Victoria), 'Anthropogenic Decay in Edward Burtynsky's Concrete Ruin Photography' – Online
- Rachel Macfarlane (Cultural Policy, University of Warwick), 'Heritage at Risk?'
- Gavin Davies (History, Independent Researcher), 'The Fungal Fix Turned Sour: Horror in The Last of Us, Resident Evil 7, and Elden Ring' – Online

Session 3: Urban decay and resistance

Chair: Nick Lawrence, University of Warwick

- Aidan Diable (History, University of Warwick), 'The Rotten Core: Discourses of Inner-Urban Decay as Integral to the Urban System'
 - David Houston Jones (Art History & Visual Culture, University of Exeter), 'Anthropocene Aesthetics and the Death Drive: Visualising Climate Change in Julian Charrière's Future Fossil Spaces (2014) and John Gerrard's Bone Work (Gulf of Mexico) (2022)'
 - Pascal Gin (French, Carleton University), "'Strontium ashes" and "strike order": on scaling nuclear landscapes in literary reportage'
 - Nan Song (English, Lancaster University), Dis/Empowering the Anthropocene: Harnessing the Energy of Decay in The MaddAddam Trilogy (2013)
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Session 4: Narrating the abject

Chair: TBC

- Martina Saric (English, University of Glasgow) 'Bodies that Decay: Infected Text/ures and Sculpted Forms in Thomas Hardy's The Well-Beloved (1897)'
- Emma Pavey (Susanna Wesley Foundation, University of Roehampton), 'Confronting irresistible decay in contemporary (peri)menopause narratives and experience'
- Hye Hyon Kim (English, Illinois State University), 'Fantomina and her Other Women: Rebirth and Reproductions of the Hyperobject' – Online
- Samia Majid (English, University of Northampton), "'The vengeance of the innocent": The Body without Organs in Frankenstein in Baghdad'

Session 5: New and old technologies

Chair: TBC

- Emma Crossey (English, King's College London) & Rachata Sasnanand (Film, King's College London), 'Tombstone Souvenirs: The Ontology of the X-Ray Image'
 - Vladimir Rosas-Salazar (Film and Television, University of Warwick), 'Magnetic Memories: Videotape Deterioration as Metaphor for Human Impermanence in Late 20th Century Memory-Makin'
 - Oriane Guiziou-Lamour (French, University of Virginia) & Jeremy Boggs (Digital Humanities, University of Virginia), 'Link Rot, Digital Decay and Internet Ephemerality'
 - Christopher O'Neill (Media Theory, Deakin University), 'The face of the child, the face of the corpse, and decay in the life-death of the biometric trace'
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Session 6: Documenting death – Online

Chair: TBC

- Meng Yi (Art theory, University of Cologne), 'Acts of Resistance: Decay, Biopolitics, and the Chinese Performative Body' – Online
- Velebita Koričančić (Communications, Anahuac Mexico University / National Autonomous University of Mexico), 'Resisting the Death Drive: Skull Motifs in Mexico City's Graffiti' – Online
- Nikita Pinto (English, St Joseph's University), 'What is your humanity worth?: Transhuman Bioethics, Death and Disability in the Pantheon series' – Online
- Benoît Loiseau (French, New York University), 'Spectacular Decay: The Broadcasting of Bodily Decline in Hervé Guibert's *La Pudeur ou l'Impudeur* (1992)' – Online

Keynote 1

**“A queer society is a ruined society”:
The irresistible decay of the contemporary anti-gender culture wars**

by Sarah Lamble

Chaired by Airelle Amédro

Since the mid-2010s, a notable surge in organised anti-transgender politics has emerged Britain and internationally, both within ‘anti-gender’ movements on the right and ‘gender critical’ feminism on the left. While older iterations of anti-LGBT+ politics were largely framed as conservative concerns around moral degeneracy, newer forms of ‘anti-gender’ politics have been reframed as cross-political concerns about safety and women’s rights. Yet both sets of logics are grounded in carceral frameworks seeking to contain threats of ruin; each framework sees sexual risk as located in the bodies of dangerous others and deviant outsiders who pose a threat to community and nation, and must be controlled through surveillance, punishment and expulsion. This paper considers how carceral logics of moral and political ruin are shaping the contemporary culture war disputes around trans rights in Britain and elsewhere. To confront these trends, the paper calls for alternative visions of safety that are grounded in queer feminist anti-carceral solidarities.

Sarah Lamble is a community organiser and Professor of Criminology & Queer Theory at Birkbeck, University of London. Lamble’s research addresses issues of gender, sexuality, and punishment, as well as alternative forms of justice. Lamble is currently researching the safety politics of the ‘gender wars’ in Britain. Lamble has served as an editorial board member for the journal Feminist Legal Studies, Trustee for the Institute of Crime and Justice Policy Research, and was previously a Visiting Scholar at the Beatrice Bain Research Group, University of California, Berkeley. Currently, Lamble is an International Advisory Editor for Theoretical Criminology, a member of the Advisory Circle for Beauty out of Ashes, and part of the Birkbeck Gender & Sexuality Studies Group (BiGS). Lamble is also co-editor of Routledge’s Social Justice Book Series. Lamble is co-founder of the Bent Bars Project, a collective that coordinates a letter-writing programme for LGBTQ+ prisoners in Britain and an organiser with Abolitionist Futures.

Keynote 2

Photographing Things in Ruins

by Corinna Wagner

Chaired by Enrica Leydi

Bodies and buildings are often compared. The body is an architecture. Buildings take the body's proportions and functions as reference, whether that body is whole, fragmented or in decay. And, of course, bodies and buildings are always in a state of ruin, sometimes fast, sometimes slow. I will present a photo essay, a visual story about this relationship and the experience of exploring ruins. There has been much debate about the ethics of photographing ruin, and bodies in ruin(s). I will add to the debate over 'ruin porn', but I am more concerned to demonstrate how ruins are archives, material relics of our past that point the way to uncertain futures. Ruin photography documents such things as environmental decay, the death of industry, radioactive histories, and the dark side of progress and development. Yet, I argue, when it comes to ruin photography, rarely is the image enough. Ruin photography needs words to lift it beyond superficiality, voyeurism, or an aestheticization of decay that pays scant attention to the social, political or environmental issues that underpin ruin.

Corinna Wagner is an Associate Professor in Literature and Visual Culture at the University of Exeter. Her interdisciplinary work bridges creative practice and critical scholarship, exploring the intersections of text and image, medical and environmental humanities, and Victorian studies. She has published on architectural and documentary photography, art and anatomy, ruins and urban design, with a particular focus on how bodies and buildings evolve, decay, and bear witness to history. Her books include *Pathological Bodies: Medicine and Political Culture* (2013), *Art & Soul: Victorians and the Gothic* (2014, with Joanne Parker), *The Oxford Handbook to Victorian Medievalism* (2020), and a forthcoming publication on art and anatomy (2026). Alongside her more traditional academic research, she works in illustrated creative nonfiction and autotheory. Her upcoming photobook *Blue Ruin* (2025) blends prose poetry, experimental photography—including cyanotype and alternative processes—and writing on ruins, ruin-making, trespass, and property. Her work has appeared in *Critical Quarterly* and exhibitions such as *Tourism* and *CoronaGothic*. Through her scholarship, photography, and creative nonfiction, Wagner challenges and reflects on disciplinary boundaries, offering new ways to engage with history, environment, and materiality.

SESSION 1

DECAYING POLICIES AND DISCOURSES

Politics of Decay: A Metaphorology of Decadence

This communication will focus on the normative implications of the imaginary of decay in contemporary political thought. More specifically, I would like to show that there exists a non-reactionary use of the metaphors of decadence in political discourse. In opposition with the reactionary fear of the end of civilization, one can celebrate it as a breach for multiplicities and pluralism. However, even though we can, should we mobilize such an imaginary? Do we want to accept the conception of time it relies on? In order to answer this question, I will follow a threefold argument. First, I will demonstrate that the political imaginary of decadence is traditionally associated with reactionary thinking. By focusing on Spengler's Decline of the West will allow me to identify the main metaphors of decadence in political discourse (I). Secondly, I will show that these metaphors have been subverted by non-reactionary thinkers such as Deleuze and Guattari in A Thousand Plateaus. I will show that such a subversion has antidemocratic implications in their work (II). Finally, I will try to identify the different fields in which this subversion of decadence may be (or is) of great interest: feminist and queer studies, ecology studies and postcolonial studies. I will try to question the legitimate political use we can make of these metaphors (III). From a methodological point of view, I will mainly rely on what Blumenberg's "metaphorology". Blumenberg argues that the study of metaphors in theoretical discourses can reveal implicit ontological claims. Metaphors are not merely rhetoric tools but participate in the conceptual process. More specifically, my work can be defined as a "political metaphorology", since I try to reveal implicit normative claims through the study of metaphors.

Arnaud Miranda (PhD, Sciences Po) is a French political theorist interested in philosophy and the history of political ideas. His dissertation, defended in December 2024, focused on the metaphors of decadence in contemporary political thought, supporting the idea that they are not exclusive to the reactionary imaginary. He published articles on the epistemological status of decadence (2021), the vegetal metaphors of civilizational decay (2024), and the role of decadence in contemporary ecological discourses (2025). In 2022, he was a Visiting Fellow at the University of Oxford and the University of Cambridge.

The death of liberal inclusion: trans rights in Tory Britain (2018- 2024)

This paper traces a significant discursive shift in attitudes to trans people in the UK between 2016 and 2024. It examines the proposals put forward by the Women and Equalities Select Committee (2016) to improve trans equality, juxtaposing them with current rhetoric in grass roots and policy settings (see, for example, Badenoch, 2024), questioning how a liberal discourse of rights and inclusion gave way to rhetoric based on exclusion (McLean, 2021; Turnbull-Dugarte and McMillan, 2023) Using a transfeminist approach, it contends that while the activism among grassroots organisations is a significant factor in current anti-trans policies and attitudes, the upsurge in hostility needs to be understood both in its broader international context (see, for example, Butler, 2024; Kuhar and Paternotte, 2017) and in relation to its amplification by figures in mainstream political parties (particularly, but not exclusively, Labour and the Conservatives). This paper therefore sheds light on the relationship between anti- gender and gender critical policy and discourses, and the particularity of the anti-gender and gender critical discourses and policy issuing from the UK as a secular state, which stands in contrast to other states with strong religious ties, such as France, Italy, and Poland, in which the state and pressure groups have pursued anti-trans policies on the basis that 'gender' as a construct harms the institution of the family (Graff and Korolczuk, 2022).

Ash Stokoe (they/them) is a Teaching Fellow in Politics and International Studies in the School of Government, University of Birmingham, whose work is at the intersection of trans studies and British politics. Most recently, Ash has worked with Dr Kit Colliver on trans and non-binary (trans+) people's experiences and perceptions of the voter ID laws recently introduced in England, Scotland, and Wales. Ash also co-wrote the article 'Transfeminist perspectives: Beyond cisnormative understandings of the digital public sphere' (2023) alongside Dr Charlotte Galpin (Birmingham) and Dr Gina Gwenffrewi (Edinburgh). Ash's current work in development focuses on trans+ people's treatment as a 'culture war' issue in Britain and the strategies of resistance trans+ people employ in response to that treatment.

The decayed discourse of global development: a premature or overdue post-mortem?

This paper adopts a Foucauldian playfulness in charting decade-long decays implied by United Nations (and relatedly intertextual) development policies. Focusing on its 'receding horizons' (Pieterse 2012: 373), I share high-level policy shifts that mirror losses of progressive capacity witnessable in everyday experience (e.g., climate, gender inequality, and economic oppression). Critiquing such policies for flattening development into a technical problem with only technical solutions (Telleria, 2017: 2144), it is widely posited that inherent flaws are discursively occluded to reduce development into a structure of slim expertise, re-enabling liberal economics to retain a long-discredited supremacy. Such analysis of 'enthralled' policies can thus be interpreted to show our era occupying an inter-reigning limbo state, where 'Gramsci's monsters' are zombified maxims which cling to deathly existence and harm scope for flourishing. However, to analogise from Tibetan traditions, development's decaying narratives may also be inhabiting their 'bardo': navigating liminal states between death/rebirth before a transmutation. My paper highlights we do have schematics for inclusive futures, galvanising scope to return into the 'bestial belly' and seek cultivable rumblings amidst a miasma of decayed rationalities. Similarly, Esteva's (2014: 151-158) scepticism of development has moved into reconsidering lived potential for convivial regeneration and commoning by 'ordinary folks' past authoritarian limits imposed in our time of epistemic 'rupture'. Yet, in scholarship and elsewhere, 'individuals over whom power is exercised are either those from whom the knowledge they themselves form will be extracted, re-transcribed, and accumulated according to new norms, or else objects of a knowledge that will also make possible new forms of control' (Foucault, 2000: 84). I thus hope to show how accumulations of new vital norms may offer escape from the material and psychic violences inflicted by decaying structures shaping and impeding wellbeing in our shared times.

Romain joined the University of Warwick in 2018 and is a Senior Teaching Fellow in Global Sustainable Development. This role includes a taught module provocatively entitled 'Surviving the Apocalypse', which dissects creeping lived dystopias under the alienating stranglehold of elite capital accumulation and explores emancipatory potential via critical thought and creative practice. Romain's research spans development, sociology, and politics in exploring globality with poststructural (Foucauldian) analysis of policy discourse alongside a recurring focus on critical development studies. Prior to pursuing academic efforts, Romain was based in London and worked on global corporate relations and high-value fundraising management for large INGOs to build development projects and respond to humanitarian emergencies.

Zombies and/or possessed bodies as form of Resistance in *Atlantics*- a transatlantic legacy

Over the past two decades, Francophone journey-based films have transitioned from focusing on anticolonial resistance and national liberation to exploring liminal spaces as sites of self-discovery and complex social dynamics. Mati Diop's *Atlantics* exemplifies this evolution by delving into the historical and cultural significance of African spirits, particularly through the portrayal of possessed bodies and reanimated female corpses. These elements, deeply rooted in West African traditions and Haitian Vodou, function as symbols of resistance against neocolonialism and the challenges of migratory crises. A central theme in *Atlantics* is the role of family, encompassing not only the living but also ancestors and spirits. This emphasis reflects a profound social and spiritual need for kinship, especially within native communities. Additionally, water is a recurring motif in the film, occupying both visual and symbolic spaces. It represents not only the perilous journey from homeland to new worlds but also the depth and expansiveness of women's desires for autonomy and agency within a patriarchal framework. This paper examines how the transformation of "possessed bodies" and "feared spirits" from revered entities into counter-narratives to necropolitics (Achille Mbembe) enables women to reclaim control over their bodies and assert self-governance. It also explores how these representations resonate with the transatlantic legacy of the Black diaspora, where sacred indigenous rituals and spiritual kinship with ancestors and deities serve as enduring symbols of resistance and survival. Through this lens, *Atlantics* affirms the power of African spirituality in articulating global narratives of resilience, autonomy, and self-determination.

Seth Compaoré is a Visiting Assistant Professor of French at Austin College (Texas, USA). His main research interests in the field of French and Francophone Cinema include border crossing, journeys of migrations in French and Francophone films, sound in Africa cinema and black transnationalism.

SESSION 2
MATERIAL DECOMPOSITION

Anthropogenic Decay in Edward Burtynsky's Concrete Ruin Photography

Concrete is a compelling visual symbol of decay in anthropogenic art. The aestheticization of decay manifests in ruin photography, a visual movement capturing the ruination of abandoned or decaying environments. Canadian photographer Edward Burtynsky's ruin photography foregrounds concrete, a material which often sinks into the background. He visualises human environmental impacts through large-scale imagery of contaminated sites of industrialisation, from the Canadian Pacific Railway system ("Railcuts #9") to coastal concrete wastelands ("Tetrapods #1"). Concrete is both a victim and perpetrator of decay, structurally breaking down over time while negatively imposing upon natural ecosystems. Burtynsky's aerial images of ecological devastation and decay simultaneously naturalise and abstractify concrete, vehemently defamiliarizing place. Though scholarship considers Burtynsky's photography through an environmental lens, little work explores the visual power of concrete in particular. This research contributes to scholarly studies of energy humanities, visual-cultural studies, and spatial theories of liminality to examine concrete ruin photography in the wake of the climate crisis. Building upon Adrian Forty's assessment of concrete's cultural history, this research examines how ruin photography redirects our attention to the environmental impacts of concrete. Deploying Bart Welling and Daniela Fargione's concept of "ecopornography," I examine voyeuristic power imbalances arising through the human consumption of visual representations of nature. Jennifer Peeples' concept of the "toxic sublime" and Nicholas Mirzoeff's decolonial methodology further interrogate ruin aesthetics. Burtynsky's ruin photography makes explicit often unseen human-altered landscapes, confronting the Eurocentric mindset through which we view environmental deterioration. By demystifying the solidity and permanence of concrete through countervisualities of decay, ruin photography exemplifies the powerful potential of arts-led regeneration in the face of the climate crisis.

Emma Dove is a graduate student pursuing a Masters of Arts in English at the University of Victoria in British Columbia, Canada. Originally from St. Thomas, Ontario, Emma has spent most of her adult life in St. John's, Newfoundland, where she attended Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador. She completed a Bachelor of Arts with an Honours in English and minor in French under the supervision of Dr. Dwayne Avery and Dr. Danine Farquharson. Her primary research field is Environmental and Energy Humanities, focusing on urban exploration narratives and concrete ruin photography. She is additionally interested in intersectional environmentalism, anthropogenic dystopia, and supernatural folklore. Emma's experience as an environmental educator at the Memorial Botanical Garden, as well as her recent research with the Pacific Seaweed Industry Association, strongly influence her commitment to environmental humanities and sustainability.

Heritage at Risk?

The Winter Gardens stand derelict on the seafront in Great Yarmouth. A space continuously re-purposed to function for business, leisure, and pleasure. This has included being used as dancehall, conference centre, ice-skating rink, German beer garden and more recently a soft play centre as cultural tastes have shifted. Nature is taking its grip on this fragile structure, bringing into focus questions surrounding its 'anticipatory' future (DeSilvey 2017), 'climate imaginaries' (Riesto, Egberts et al. 2021) of its position on the seafront for the 'reshaping of this heritage landscape' (Egberts 2018). The Winter Gardens is one of thousands of buildings on Historic England's Heritage at Risk register. Listed as a Grade II*, the structure grows more and more fragile from the toll of the strong North Sea winds, shifting sands and local wildlife ecology. Where decay can add patina to romantic ruins in rural landscapes, in other places it epitomises a sense of loss from the prosperity of industrial pasts. For now, the building cannot be discarded or destroyed due to a combination of its listed status and the emotional attachment held by residents nostalgic for past times. This paper will explore decay within the frame of the Anthropocene and heritage conservation to question our belief in the importance of saving heritage sites. It considers how our cultural framing of heritage at risk may deny alternative possibilities for change and regrowth. The conditions for one type of heritage to thrive can be at odds with another and where something has been lost, something new can flourish (Tsing 2015). The idea of managed decay (Desilvey 2017) in the conservation of heritage sites of scientific interest is gaining traction but stands at odds with our obsession with preservation.

Rachel Macfarlane is a part-time PhD student researching Cultural Policy at the University of Warwick, funded by Midlands4Cities. Her multi-disciplinary thesis examines emotional attachment and cultural value in relation to seaside heritage, cultural policy and regeneration. She works part-time for the National Lottery Heritage Fund as a Senior Engagement Manager, providing advice and guidance to organisations with responsibility for heritage sites. This includes working closely with Historic England and Arts Council England to respond to challenges and opportunities within the cultural sector. Rachel has a background of working in museums, is an Associate of the Museums Association, Museum Mentor to two Suffolk museums and Chairs the Women Cultural Leaders East group.

The Fungal Fix Turned Sour: Horror in *The Last of Us*, *Resident Evil 7*, and *Elden Ring*

In contrast to the hopeful depiction of fungi as solutions to ecological and economic crises, this paper argues that video games like *The Last of Us* (Sony Computer Entertainment, 2013), *Resident Evil 7* (Capcom, 2017), and *Elden Ring* (Bandai Namco Entertainment, 2022) present mycological forms as sources of horror and dystopia. These games depict fungi not as symbols of survival or regeneration but as forces of contagion, decay, and annihilation. This shift stands in opposition to the optimistic mycological narratives found in fiction and nonfiction such as Silvia Moreno-García's *Mexican Gothic* (2020), Merlin Sheldrake's *Entangled Life* (2020), James S. A. Corey's *Expanse* series (2011-22), Karin Tidbeck's *Amatka* (2012), Larissa Lai's *Tiger Flu* (2018), and Tade Thompson's *The Wormwood Trilogy* (2016-19). In these works, fungi are frequently framed as offering a path to survival, a potential means to sustain life where it otherwise would not be possible, whether through healing properties or alternative ecosystems. The video games, however, reverse this narrative, framing fungi as destructive and invasive rather than life-sustaining. In *The Last of Us*, the cordyceps fungus transforms humans into monstrous creatures, erasing any possibility of redemption through nature. *Resident Evil 7* uses mould and fungal growth to generate grotesque, parasitic mutations that threaten human existence, while *Elden Ring* situates fungi within a decaying world, embodying cycles of death and corruption. These representations disrupt the idealised notion of fungi as eco-friendly saviours, offering instead a vision of fungi as agents of irreversible collapse. This comparative analysis highlights the tension between utopian and dystopian portrayals of fungi in contemporary media. While fiction and nonfiction often present mycological life as a symbol of resilience and renewal, these games turn that vision on its head, using fungi to explore the darker, more horrifying possibilities of ecological crisis.

Gavin Davies, an independent scholar, recently completed his PhD in History at the University of Exeter. His thesis, "Rules Britannia: Board Games, Britain, and the World, c.1759-1860," funded by the South, West, and Wales Doctoral Training Partnership, argues that the imperial impact of Georgian and Victorian board games has been overstated. His research interests include the cultural and social dimensions of games and interactive media. He has contributed several articles, conference papers, and book chapters on esports, video games, and games culture to forthcoming publications with Palgrave Macmillan and De Gruyter.

SESSION 3

URBAN DECAY AND RESISTANCE

The Rotten Core: Discourses of Inner-Urban Decay as Integral to the Urban System

Cities are inherently places of decay – pollution, disease, poverty, and crime. For at least the past three centuries in the Anglophone world, decay has dominated urban discourses. Yet there has never been consensus on what urban decay is, much less on its causes and effects. Municipal authorities and academics have often understood it as no more than an unfortunate by-product of urban processes; a problem to be solved or mitigated. However, historians of the urban have often recognised that decay, and the discourses around it, occupy a more complex role within the city. This paper, then, seeks to resituate urban decay not merely as a destructive by-product, but as an integral and often generative force within the urban system. To do so, the paper will adopt a transnational and comparative approach, examining decay's omnipresence in and its generative effects on the cities of the Anglophone world at the height of their industrial urbanisation: the turn of the twentieth century. It will examine political, scientific, journalistic, and artistic representations of the inner cities of Liverpool (UK), Melbourne (Australia), and San Francisco (US) as in decay – materially, biologically, and morally – and explore how they provoked processes of suburban expansion, inner-city renewal, and even the formation of national identities. It hopes to open new perspectives on cities, not as antagonised by decay, but as partly constituted by it. It seeks to leave an impression of the city as a paradoxical partnership between 'splendour and squalor'.

Aidan Diable is a first-year PhD student in the Department of History, jointly studying at the University of Warwick and Monash University. His research interests span urban, social, intellectual, and transnational history. His thesis, *The Materialisation of Ideas in the Suburbs of Nineteenth and Early-Twentieth Century Liverpool, UK, and Melbourne, Australia*, is supervised by Pierre Purseigle (Warwick), Lionel Frost, and Kate Murphy (Monash). Aidan's research is a comparative study of how the suburban ideal—and the various discourses that shaped it—materialized in the built and social environments of Liverpool and Melbourne. His work examines whether the suburbs of both cities represent manifestations of the same 'Victorian suburban ideal' and, if so, why they developed in such distinct ways. More broadly, his research explores the ways in which ideas take material form in urban environments, how they circulate globally, and how urban and suburban spaces are shaped.

Anthropocene Aesthetics and the Death Drive: Visualising Climate Change in Julian Charrière's Future Fossil Spaces (2014) and John Gerrard's Bone Work (Gulf of Mexico) (2022)

In this paper, I consider two art works which respond to climate change, a concept which, despite its urgent threat to human life, continues to receive an 'aesthetic' treatment in visual media. Gerrard's Bone Work (2022) centres on sixteen fragments of dead coral found by the artist on the shores of the Yucatán Peninsula on the Gulf Of Mexico, and which become the building blocks of a generative art work which is both interactive and of potentially infinite duration. Julian Charrière's Future Fossil Spaces (2014), meanwhile, heralds future devastation, signalling the fate which is likely to befall the Salar de Uyúni, the largest salt flat in the world, and a key site in the nascent Bolivian lithium mining industry. The work signals both formal simulation and an indexical relation to place, incorporating material taken from Salar de Uyúni itself. Both works defamiliarise the insistently recirculated iconography of climate change seen in the limited and aestheticised visual repertoire of melting glaciers and stranded polar bears deployed in media coverage and art. Gerrard and Charrière, instead, produce objects which, like Morton's (2013) concept of the 'hyperobject', are 'nonlocal' and enjoy temporalities other than those of the human. Here, I evaluate Mia M. Bennett's account (2020) of the dominance of the picturesque and the sublime within 'anthropocene aesthetics'. Charrière and Gerrard suggest important ways, in new media and installation art, in which such an aesthetics may be contested.

David Houston Jones is Professor of French and Visual Culture, University of Exeter. He works at the intersection of visual, medical and forensic epistemologies, and is the author of Visual Culture and the Forensic (2022), Installation Art and the Practices of Archivalism (2016) and Samuel Beckett and Testimony (2011). He co-edited Samuel Beckett and Contemporary Art (with Rob Reginio and Katherine Weiss, 2017) and Paddy Hartley: of Faces and Facades (with Marjorie Gehrhardt, 2015). He was UK PI on the INTERREG IVa-funded project 1914FACES2014, and subsequently co-edited a special issue of the Journal of War and Culture Studies (2017) entitled Assessing the Legacy of the Gueules cassées: from Surgery to Art.

"Strontium ashes" and "strike order": on scaling nuclear landscapes in literary reportage

Observed in the vicinity of secured installations: two dead shrews "still free of any rot", a stack of "crumbling" pylons. Discarded by a stretch of deserted highway: animal droppings, a "grease-smattered" white glove, some cans "rusting away". As evidenced from Jean Rolin's *Le Pont de Bezons* (2019) and Antonio Pagnotta's *Le Dernier Homme de Fukushima* (2013), the trope of assemblage may well be a feature of pedestrian narratives investigating inter- or peri-urban spaces. Motorways and infrastructural sites are arguably locations of choice from where to report on entangled instances of organic and material decay. Beyond assemblage as a shared technique, both texts engage with matters of decomposition in the direct or distant proximity of nuclear landscapes. Pagnotta's book-length reportage locates the narrator face down in the infamous forbidden zone around the failed Dai-ichi nuclear plant. Rolin's dilettante reporting along a stretch of the river Seine draws him to an off-limits nuclear transmitting station. In either case, decomposing trash observed in passing is brought within the scope of an expanded narrative, aimed at the fall-out of nuclear disaster or the reach of nuclear infrastructures. Drawing from this limited corpus of comparison, we will probe such scalar implications as literary journalism turns its investigative gaze to the representation of decay. Issues of scales will first be analysed in terms of temporal regimes, spatial configurations and ontological orders straddling the human and non-human. Subsequently, the focus of enquiry will shift internally. We will consider how the self-reflexive performance of literary journalism — as a genre routinely scaling facts and events to localized investigation —, deals with deteriorated mobility experienced as a nuclear-related side-effect. In conclusion, we will enquire to what extent these two narrative accounts can be interpreted through the lens of Ulrich Beck's "emancipatory catastrophism" (2016) as contributing aesthetics of scalable "visibility".

Pascal Gin holds a Ph.D. in comparative literature from Université de Montréal. He is Associate Professor in the Institute for Comparative Studies in Literature, Art and Culture and the Department of French at Carleton University (Ontario, Canada). His areas of research and publication cover mobility studies, literary journalism, contemporary French literature and translation studies.

Dis/Empowering the Anthropocene: Harnessing the Energy of Decay in *The MaddAddam Trilogy* (2013)

The decay process involves the dynamics of energy flows, emphasising negotiations over the distribution of energy to empower or disempower energy systems shared by human and nonhuman life forms. At a time when energy depletion and waste disposal exacerbate climate and ecological crises, this paper examines the decay of organic waste in Margaret Atwood's *The MaddAddam Trilogy* (2013), exploring how decay can reimagine energy and waste futures and multi-species justice. Drawing on waste studies, ecocriticism, and energy humanities, this paper argues that the process of decay in the trilogy is inevitably shaped by anthropogenic intervention during the post-oil energy transition. Residual oil capitalism violently disrupts the natural decay of humans and animals in pleeblands, reviving oil ideologies through the refinement of 'garboil', which signifies a form of 'petro-nostalgia' or a 'destructive attachment' to oil (LeMenager 2014). In contrast, in *God's Garden*, gardeners ingeniously utilise decay energy, forming a heterogeneous alliance (Tang, 2022) through solar power and animate energy, indicating a return from the exosomatic energy regime to the somatic energy regime. By focusing on the self-sufficient bodily structures of the humanoid Crakers, this paper contends that nonhuman Crakers deconstruct binaries between life and death, human and non-human, decay and reproduction, offering an alternative vision of energy and waste futures - one that transcends petro-attachment while challenging the uncritical celebration of agrarian resilience.

Nan Song is an AHRC-NWCDTP funded Ph.D. student in English Literature at Lancaster University. Her Ph.D. project, titled 'Reframing Waste: Imagining Apocalyptic Waste Disposal in Contemporary Speculative Fiction', explores how speculative fiction combines waste with capitalist crises in the Anthropocene, while investigating intersections and tensions among the fields of speculative fiction, waste studies, and ecocriticism. Her research interests include waste studies, speculative fiction, ecocriticism, environmental humanities, energy humanities, and the Anthropocene.

SESSION 4
NARRATING THE ABJECT

Bodies that Decay: Infected Text/ures and Sculpted Forms in Thomas Hardy's The Well-Beloved (1897)

'I am interested in language because it wounds or seduces me', said Roland Barthes in Pleasure of the Text. Using Barthes as a point of departure, my talk explores the notion that fictional language both wounds (form of infections, marks, scratches on the skin) and seduces (stories of moving statues). Using Thomas Hardy's novel, The Well-Beloved (1897) as a case study, I address how Hardy's rich imagery of physical substance and sculpted forms reflects a keen interest in the material existence and the corruption of the human body. In focusing on the sculptures described in the novel, I appraise the dual meaning of demarcation – signifying both the boundary, the limit (between dead and living) as well in its other meaning to mark (to bruise, cut or harm). Through the inflicted marks or cuts (to the stone, to woman's flesh) Hardy's narrative usurps the life-death boundary. The story reveals what Kenneth Gross (The Dream of the Moving Statue), calls a 'phantasmatic pattern' – the notion that the presence of statues infects and influences the living who encounter it. What is at stake in the Well-Beloved is an infection that spreads across the body of text – the statues never-made, or completed, wound all living. My argument is that the presence/absence of statues in the novel is a form of verbal aberrant tissue – instead of stone Galatea transformed into flesh, the text implies unexplained moments of unhealthy stone-flesh mixtures. Through the sculptor's obsession with bodies (animate/inanimate, women/statues), I ask: how can the idea of contamination bring interactions between organic forms and inorganic matter into sharper focus? How does the concept of the limit demonstrate different spheres of existence? What else comes to life in the liminal space – where the living meet the dead, where the stone is conflated with infected flesh?

Martina Saric is a researcher in Victorian Literature at the University of Glasgow. She teaches English Literature & Creative Writing at the University of Glasgow and the University of Strathclyde. Her research focuses on Victorian literature, Pre-Raphaelites, body and sensuality, surrealist art, aspects of visuality, film image and philosophy of Gaston Bachelard. Her writing explores sensorial knowledge, focusing on the body and modes of embodiment from the nineteenth century to the present.

Confronting irresistible decay in contemporary (peri)menopause narratives and experience

We will examine the interplay of literal and metaphorical decay in the context of (peri)menopause, engaging with themes and metaphors such as monstrosity, agency, abject shame, ecology and the performance of menopause itself through selected literature and film (including Fargeat 2024, Miller 2022 and Steinke 2019). I'll propose that this experience forces an assessment of one's desire for control over one's body and identity, and one's willingness to let go and grieve when confronted with (ultimately) irresistible decay. Jermyn (2023) describes the 'menopausal turn', the recent explosion of books, film and social media content around menopause (along with supplements and other therapies), much of which exhorts the afflicted to 'take charge of' or 'manage' one's menopause so as to avoid the appearance or experience of what Robert Wilson famously termed the "horror of this living decay" (1966) and its culturally-engendered shame. In a medical model of deficiency, disease and decay, youth is normative (and the associated media skews white, cisgender and privileged, as Jermyn shows). To be agentive here is to 'treat symptoms'. Is this a blunt denial of decay, and indeed death? If medical interventions can onset or delay biological decay, why not take advantage? Transhumanist-leaning narratives bump up here against the 'natural' purity of a 'life transition' perspective (the latter often opposed to the perceived artifice of HRT). Attempts at a kind of aestheticization can be another type of management of menopausal decay, reaching for sense-making imagery and ritual through embodied practice, sloughing off literal fertility to reveal a richer fecundity, reconfiguring gender, transfiguring shame, facing absurdity. Menopause isn't only about the ending aspect of decay. It might also be about begetting, about hope, intersectional empathy and action. The irresistible decay of menopause, and its perspectives, might serve too, I'll suggest, as a metaphor for the climate crisis.

Emma Pavey is a researcher and research communications manager at the Susanna Wesley Foundation, University of Roehampton. Her interdisciplinary background includes a PhD in Linguistics (Sussex), a ThM in Theology, and postgraduate qualifications in Restorative Justice and Adult Education. Her research, publications and activities span these areas, with making space as an underpinning value. Most recently she has focused on the lived experience of menopause, mostly in the hope it will help her make sense of her own life, or at least live with the mystery a little better.

Fantomina and her Other Women: Rebirth and Reproductions of the Hyperobject

With women's desires to "do away with them completely," and her children to be listed as her husband's property in eighteenth-century England, there is limited room for a woman's sexual agency or rights (Anderson 1). However, if a woman was to reproduce herself with objects to turn into a community of women of different social class and experience, the patriarchal rules become ambiguous as to how to restrain her body. Eliza Haywood's protagonist in *Fantomina; or Love in a Maze* (1725) demonstrates the fluidity of her body by using objects of disguise to turn herself into an hyperobject, a futural looming presence, that is familiar with one's death. This enables her to be dead as one and live as another and choose her identity as multiple rebirth and decay of her body. Her only purpose is to fulfill her desires and reclaim her agency from the night of her sexual assault, as she is pushed to negotiate her presence as a ruined maid, or a living illusion of her creation. By performing multiple roles as a sex worker Fantomina, a young innocent maid Celia, a mourning widow Bloomer, and an unknown mystery woman called Incognita, she uses her body as a non-living object and to bring allure to her necrophiliac body and abject her opponent, Beauplaisir and succeed in making him the object of her desire. By using Katherine Behair's theory object-oriented-feminism, the protagonist subverts the gendered rules of sexuality by expressing plasticity, a feature that is "flexible yet resistant" exhibiting the extreme measures she undergoes in a risk society that calls her existence dead.

Hye Hyon Kim is a PhD Candidate from Illinois State University writing her dissertation "Women Written by Women and the Integrated Subjectivity: Disguise and the Objectified Self" Her research areas include 18th and 19th century British literature, looking specifically at female characters and their personal relationships with objects that allow disguise, social mobility, and agency by using the theoretical lens Object Oriented Feminism.

The vengeance of the innocent": The Body without Organs in Frankenstein in Baghdad

This paper will examine how the fragmenting, decaying body of the titular monster in Ahmed Saadawi's *Frankenstein in Baghdad* (2013) reflects the violent logic of the Iraq War. I interpret Saadawi's monster through Deleuze and Guattari's theory of the Body without Organs, described as "an assemblage of organs freed from the supposedly 'natural' or 'instinctual' organization that makes it an organism" (Holland 94). The monster is in a constant state of disintegration, and therefore freed from the "natural" boundaries that govern life and death. Composed of the victims of the war, he is forced to replenish his rotting frame with body parts littering the streets of Baghdad in order to keep himself alive. The novel evokes Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (1818), a condemnation of the transgressive values of a rationalist, post-enlightenment world that escalates reason to its logical extremes, culminating in Victor Frankenstein's monstrous creation. As Fred Botting notes, "monstrosity may provide, at least temporarily, figures to apprehend the nonsensical excesses of war and horror, giving vent to inchoate anxieties or uncontrollable energies" (15). In Saadawi's retelling, the monster is a perverted manifestation of the American-led invasion of Iraq, filling a power vacuum in Baghdad and proclaiming himself "the vengeance of the innocent" (137). He is an assemblage of the processes of decay and regeneration, producing corpses (by engaging in vigilante killings) as much as his physical body is produced by corpses. The monster signifies an endless state of becoming, both as a product of neoliberalism's endless logic of destruction — and, therefore, a critique of it — and an agent of its worst excesses. His existence is a critique of the declining social, economic and political conditions that create, and render his existence, abject.

Samia Majid is a final-year PhD Candidate and Associate Lecturer at the University of Northampton. In 2022, she was awarded a University Studentship to study a Doctor of Philosophy in English and Creative Writing by the University of Northampton. Her thesis examines literary depictions of individual liberty and 'self-making' under neoliberalism in contemporary world fiction. In June 2024, Samia co-organised the 'Contemporary Cultural Responses to a Neoliberal World' Symposium, which was funded by the Centre for Cultural and Literary Studies at the University of Northampton.

SESSION 5

NEW AND OLD TECHNOLOGIES

Tombstone Souvenirs: The Ontology of the X-Ray Image

The 1895 discovery of X-rays inflamed the public imagination, to the extent that the intense period after their discovery is commonly known as 'X-ray mania'. 1 Shelves were 'ransacked' for X-ray equipment, as members of the public sought to gaze on their own skeletal image. 2 This paper questions the ontology of the X-ray image. It will first interrogate the early, enthusiastic response to X-ray imagery which occurred alongside recognition of their morbidity: 'these tombstone- souvenirs unpleasant'. 3 It will also consider how these images of decay re-framed the relationship of the human to the non-human. Early X-rays were widely understood as a form of photography. In addition to exploring the fascinating public reaction, this paper will consider the parallels between 'standard' photography and X-ray photography, with similarities in reception and mechanism. Drawing its title from André Bazin's 'Ontology of the Photographic Image' (1945) - which suggests a driver of photography is a desire to preserve life - this paper questions the motivations behind X-ray enthusiasm, when X-rays deliver such seemingly opposing products. Ultimately, despite being a product of modernity, this paper argues that the X-ray provided a confronting reminder of what it meant to be human. In the wake of On the Origin of Species, it removed the boundaries between the human and the animal. Its valuable reminders of materiality are particularly timely given current environmental concerns. This paper is interdisciplinary, not only in content, but as a product of two separate areas of PhD research, working across Literature, Film, Philosophy and the Medical Humanities.

Emma Crossey is a PhD student at King's College London whose research explores the prevalence of skeletal imagery throughout the works of Virginia Woolf. Emma graduated with a BA in Ancient History and English from the University of Exeter (2014) and an MA in modernism from UCL (2015). Emma has spent the last eight years working mostly in the charity sector, managing Digital Fundraising at organisations such as Unicef UK, Alzheimer's Society and Crisis UK.

Rachata Sasnanand is a PhD student at King's College London whose research concerns a new theoretical framework he calls the 'material gaze', which examines how certain cinematic practices of the last 20-30 years have attempted to align the spectator with nonhuman perspectives, positioning such practices as a reaction to the climate crisis. He graduated with a BA in English Literature from the University of Exeter, and an MA in Film Studies from King's College London.

Magnetic Memories: Videotape Deterioration as Metaphor for Human Impermanence in Late 20th Century Memory-Makin

In the final decades of the 20th century, families around the world turned to videotape as a way to preserve their most precious memories, unwittingly participating in a profound technological and cultural experiment in memory preservation. In this presentation, I will explore a paradox at the heart of VHS technology: its dual nature as both a preservation medium and an inherently degrading artifact. By examining how videotape's material decay intersects with our cultural anxieties about memory, mortality, and technological obsolescence, we can better understand our complex relationship with personal archives (and memory practices). This investigation draws from both archival research and personal home video collections from the 1990s and 2000s, revealing how the aesthetics of degrading videotape—its characteristic visual artifacts, colour distortions, and audio deterioration—have become inseparable from the memories they were meant to preserve, creating a unique form of mediated remembrance that actively incorporates decay into its meaning-making process. Building on Ina Blom's (2016) conceptualisation of video as a memory-like machine and Laura Marks' (1997) theory of haptic visuality, I show how the visible deterioration of magnetic tapes creates an affective relationship between viewers and their recorded past. My analysis suggests that videotape's material vulnerability, manifested through processes like magnetic erosion and binder hydrolysis, serves as a powerful metaphor for human temporal existence. The format's inherent contradictions—being simultaneously an archival medium and a self-erasing document—reveal deeper cultural attitudes toward preservation and loss in late 20th century memory practices. Overall, this presentation suggesting that videotape deterioration represents a unique form of 'collaborative decay,' where technological breakdown becomes an active participant in memory formation rather than merely its enemy.

Vladimir Rosas-Salazar is an academic researcher specialising in Film Studies. He completed his PhD in the Department of Film and Television Studies at the University of Warwick, where he currently serves as an Associate Tutor. His research interests centre on media and memory practices withindomestic contexts.

Link Rot, Digital Decay and Internet Ephemerality

In his 2000 book *Designing Web Usability*, the “guru of Web page usability”. Jakob Nielsen coined the term “link rot” to describe a growing concern on the Internet: the ephemerality of web links. Since then, this example of “digital decay” has only increased: “a quarter of all web pages that existed at one point between 2013 and 2023 are no longer available”. Metaphors of the organic permeates concerns surrounding the transience of the internet: “longevity”, “broken”, “impermanent”, “dead”, “rot”, and “decay”. In this paper, we examine questions of decay from a digital humanities standpoint, exploring the tension between the idea that everything can (and must) stay alive on the internet, and contemporary calls for graceful degradation and degrowth. Through a case-study of broken links gathered from the [Index of Digital Humanities Conference Abstracts](#) which analyzes data from conference abstracts spanning sixty-three years, we shift conversation from how we can ensure the robustness of internet links and digital permanence to why should everything be permanent? How can we balance the conservation of information and making peace with the internet as an archive of traces, and the “fine art of disappearance”? Our stance moves beyond recognizing or embracing brokenness and decay; Instead, we seek to find methods—philosophical and material—for making, and making with, the humus of digital decay

Oriane Guiziou-Lamour is a fourth-year doctoral candidate in the Department of French at the University of Virginia. She is interested in the relationship between power, sexuality and gender. In her dissertation, she explores the birth of the “*érotico-sentimental*” genre at the end of the eighteenth century. This work allows her to unearth texts written by authors like Suzanne Giroust de Morency, Félicité de Choiseul-Meuse, and Marie Guénard de Méré, while discussing topics such as female expression of sexuality in the eighteenth century, lesbian representation, and the active effort of nineteenth-century politics in erasing women authors from the French literary canon. She has also published several articles on the expression of female desire in erotic works written by women, sadomasochism, lesbian vampirism in movies, ero-guro manga, as well as a short story on agricultural gore and lesbian cannibalism.

Jeremy Boggs is the Head of Research & Development in the Scholars' Lab, University of Virginia Library. He has been a digital humanities practitioner for over twenty years, as a designer, developer, researcher, and teacher. His current research includes feminist interface design for digital collections, homebrewed adaptations of fictional and historical materials for [Dungeons and Dragons](#) and connecting bibliographies to different types of card decks and games.

The face of the child, the face of the corpse, and decay in the life-death of the biometric trace

Facial Recognition Technologies (FRTs) have emerged as the key biometric for automating processes of identification within the contemporary state. Military-industrial FRT research is fixated upon the problematic of illegibility, which it operationalises as a way of developing the emergent potential of the biometric apparatus. In particular, the face of the child and that of the corpse have been taken up by researchers as exemplars of the confounding mutability of the face as vital phenomena. The growth of the child demands a technical simulation of its unruly becoming; the decomposition of the corpse necessitates the modelling of organic decay. The child then is too lively, and the corpse too undead, for FRT to easily model. The ‘failure’ of the child and the corpse to grow and to rest in the expected or desired way means that they are highly productive in expanding FRT’s horizon of technical experimentation and possibility. In this paper I will consider how this modelling of the face of the child and the face of the corpse enframes ‘life-death’ within a new iteration of the biopolitical order. I argue that military-industrial researchers exploit the illegibility of the face in a productive dialectic which thrives upon the ambivalence of the vital-mortal body in order to legitimise and expand the operation of the biometric apparatus.

Dr Christopher O'Neill is a Deakin University Postdoctoral University Researcher at the Alfred Deakin Institute for Citizenship and Globalisation (Australia) and a 2025-2026 Fulbright Postdoctoral Scholar at the University of Southern California. His work considers the way that ‘the human’ is being refigured within contemporary automated technologies, amidst a new iteration of the biopolitical order.

SESSION 6
DOCUMENTING DEATH

Acts of Resistance: Decay, Biopolitics, and the Chinese Performative Body

This paper examines the representation of bodily harm in contemporary Chinese performance art as a critique of normative collapse during socio-political transformations. Drawing on Julia Kristeva's abjection theory and Michel Foucault's biopolitics, the study explores how Chinese artists employ the body to challenge societal norms surrounding morality, purity, and agency. Zhang Huan's 12 Square Meters (1994) stages the artist's naked body, smeared with honey and fish oil, in a dilapidated public restroom, attracting swarms of flies. This endurance-based performance critiques urban alienation and the fragility of bodily integrity in polluted environments. Yin xiuzhen's Washing the River (1995) reflects on personal and collective trauma by immersing herself in natural waters, transforming acts of cleansing into rituals of healing and renewal. He Yunchang's One Meter of Democracy (2010) further expands this discourse, inviting an audience to vote on whether the artist should endure a one-meter incision along his torso, foregrounding the tensions between individual pain and collective decision-making. These performances illuminate the collapse of normative systems in post-socialist China, revealing tensions between individual expression and collective ideology. They present bodily harm as both a critique of entrenched power structures and a reimagining of agency, identity, and social renewal. By situating these works within the broader dynamics of decay and regeneration, this paper argues that decay, often perceived as destructive, can serve as a transformative force for envisioning new possibilities in artistic and social discourses. It further underscores how Chinese performance art engages with global concerns surrounding biopolitics, moral rupture, and the interrelations of death and life.

Meng Yi is a Ph.D. candidate in Art and Art Theory at the University of Cologne, specializing in the intersections of body politics and contemporary Chinese art. Her research focuses on the representation of the body in post-socialist China, examining themes of gender, power, and artistic agency. Her current dissertation, Embodied Narratives: Body Politics in Contemporary Chinese Artistic Discourse, investigates how the body serves as a site of resistance and regeneration in visual culture. Meng Yi also actively participates in cross-cultural art collaborations, using her academic and curatorial practices to foster dialogue on identity and social transformation.

Resisting the Death Drive: Skull Motifs in Mexico City's Graffiti

This paper explores the skull motif in Mexico City's graffiti art as an emblem of decay, critiquing socio-political realities and reflecting the cyclical convergence of life and death. Embedded in the urban landscape, these uncommissioned artworks serve as mementos mori and address issues such as gentrification and the commodification of cultural symbols. Positioned in public spaces, they challenge the sanitization and touristification of urban decay, offering an alternative narrative that underscores its dual physical and metaphorical presence. The skull, a symbol deeply embedded in Mexican cultural heritage, particularly during Día de los Muertos celebrations, adds a layer to the critique of modern social issues, enhancing the motif's historical and cultural significance. Analyzed through cultural critique and visual analysis, the skull motifs serve as contemporary ruins that resonate with fascination with decay. Focusing on murals in the neighborhood of Narvarte, the study highlights how these artworks echo socio-economic concerns and portray decay as both a marker of cultural decline and a potential for regeneration. This research illustrates how street art acts as a site of resistance against capitalism's 'death drive'—its compulsion to commodify death and decay. It discusses how the physical degradation depicted parallels social fragmentation within capitalist societies. By mediating experiences of decay, the art fosters an understanding of its role in shaping public perceptions and discourses on life and death. The paper advocates for a reevaluation of the aesthetic and functional roles of urban art in the discourse on decay, questioning whether artistic depictions of decay can indeed catalyze cultural and urban resurgence.

Velebita Koričančić is an Assistant Professor at Anahuac University Mexico's School of Communications and an Adjunct Professor in literature at the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM). Originally from Zagreb, Croatia, she is now based in Mexico City, where she earned her Ph.D. in Literature with honors from UNAM and an MA in Latin American Studies (cum laude) from the University of Salamanca, Spain. A recognized researcher, she is a Candidate-level member of Mexico's National System for Research (2024–2027). She has worked as a literary translator and served in Mexico City's Ministry of Culture, curating literary events. In 2025, she will chair the panel Reframing Madness: Arts at the Intersection of Mental Health and Mad Studies at the College Art Association's Annual Conference in New York.

What is your humanity worth?: Transhuman Bioethics, Death and Disability in the Pantheon series

In episode 2 of *Pantheon*, a telecom tycoon resembling Mukesh Ambani, the notorious Indian billionaire, murders Mumbai slum dwellers in horrific experiments to create UIs or Uploaded Intelligence. Lured with the promise of money and welfare, the slum dwellers, all nameless, are disposable bodies—tortured and stripped of personhood in their digital afterlives. In this space of biotechnological experimentation, they become ‘bare life’ (Agamben) where persons legally reduced to the status of mere life may be subjected to violence with impunity. This research applies Agamben’s notion of ‘bare life’ to interpret the bioethical dilemmas present in *Pantheon* (2022 -2023), a science fiction animated series. Based on Ken Liu’s short stories, the animated series is set in a futuristic world where most countries, including India are embroiled in a UI arms race, to upload the human consciousness of their most brilliant researchers and in the process, achieve global supremacy. The disembodied UIs are seen as former humans by the embodied, and wrestle with issues of personhood. These issues about personhood are further exacerbated with the introduction of clones and humanoid bodies to house UIs. The series raises a number of questions in this regard: Is ‘deleting’ an uploaded human brain akin to murder? Can digital life allow one to transcend death, disability and illness? Is such a possibility utopian, and if so, should all humans opt for transcending these bodily “limitations”? Are the disembodied capable of feeling true emotions and pain? Are clones mere copies of the ‘original’, or are they capable of autonomous action? These questions ultimately highlight the overarching issue of which bodies must be rendered productive and which expendable. As Melinda Hall argues, debates about human enhancement in bioethics literature are fundamentally tied to the notion of disability, that is, they are “conditioned by assumptions about what makes life worth living and who should live” (10). In the series, a number of characters suffering with terminal illnesses, comatose conditions, and disabilities align themselves with transhumanist philosophy and opt for digital immortality. In doing so, the technology in *Pantheon* posits a ‘thanatopolitics,’ where the death of these characters becomes a productive power for their governments who utilize their “sacrifice” for further research and political power. This chapter therefore draws on posthumanism and disability studies, to examine how the biotechnological project of UIs in *Pantheon* reinforces transhumanist beliefs of bodily perfection, and in doing so serves to dehumanize vulnerable bodies.

Nikita Gloria Pinto is an Assistant Professor in the Department of English, St Joseph’s University, Bangalore, India. She holds an M.Phil. from the University of Madras, and an M.A. in English Literature from the University of Delhi. An enthusiast of crime writing, she has previously published essays on narratives of female criminality and monstrosity in historical crime fiction and true crime narratives. Her latest publication includes a chapter in *Certainty and Ambiguity in Global Mystery Fiction* (published by Bloomsbury Academic, 2024) which examines moral ambiguity and vigilante justice in Indian crime fiction. Apart from crime fiction, her research interests focus on popular culture, science-fiction, freak studies, disability studies, and superhero narratives.

Spectacular Decay: The Broadcasting of Bodily Decline in Hervé Guibert’s *La Pudeur ou l’Impudeur* (1992)

On 16 March 1990, Hervé Guibert announced his retirement. “I no longer write,” declared the 35-year-old French writer on the set of the literary programme *Apostrophes*, while promoting his novel *À l’ami qui ne m’a pas sauvé la vie* (1990). “After this book, I don’t see what else I could write,” he concluded, visibly emaciated by the progression of AIDS. Following this public withdrawal, television producer Pascale Breugnot contacted him and, instead of writing, offered him the opportunity to make a film in which he would be “both the author and the subject.” Guibert, who had always dreamed of becoming a filmmaker, agreed and spent the next ten months documenting the decay of his body with a camcorder. Titled *La Pudeur ou l’impudeur*, the film was broadcast on the national channel TF1 on 30 January 1992, a few weeks after his death. Described by Guibert as “one of the strangest documentaries ever,” it became one of the first films in France to depict the subjective experience of a person living with AIDS. In contrast to the alternative media practices emerging at the same time within New York’s activist groups, *La Pudeur* was profoundly marked by the nascent methods of French reality television: “A particularly pernicious form of symbolic violence,” as Pierre Bourdieu described it. In this paper, I will analyse the film’s production context in order to critically reflect on the ethics and politics of broadcasting the author’s declining body. In particular, I will discuss the ways in which Breugnot intended to make a spectacle of Guibert’s death and, in turn, how Guibert resisted the objectification of his own death.

Benoît Loiseau is a scholar of French and Comparative Literature. He is currently a “Marie Curie” (MSCA) Postdoctoral Fellow at University Paris 8 | Vincennes – Saint-Denis and a Visiting Researcher at NYU’s Department of French Literature, Thought and Culture. Prior to this, he was a Postdoctoral Researcher at the University of Geneva’s Institute for Gender Studies. His research is concerned with the cultural discourses of gender and sexuality with an emphasis on aesthetics, the medical humanities and contemporary philosophy. His first book, *The Anti-Clinic: Radical Experiments in the Art of Care*, is forthcoming in 2026 from Fitzcarraldo Editions in the United Kingdom and Yale University Press in North America.

